

Biography: Bruce Ing

Steven L. Stephenson¹

¹ Department of Biological Sciences, University of Arkansas, Fayetteville AR 72701, United States of America

E-mail: slsteph@uark.edu

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Abstract: This is a summary of the contributions that Bruce Ing, a field biologist and recognized myxomycetologist, has accomplished. Bruce was the one of the founders of the International Congress on the Systematics and Ecology of Myxomycetes (ICSEM), an event that takes place on a regular basis in different parts of the world.

Keywords: environmentalism, field biology, myxomycetes, United Kingdom.

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Introduction

Bruce Ing was born on September 1, 1937 in London, England. He was educated at the City College of London School, Cambridge University, St. Andrews University, and Liverpool University, receiving his B.S., M.A., M.Sc. and Ph.D. degrees. From 1960-1964, he was an Assistant Organiser of the Conservation Corps (where his job was to organize the conservation management of nature reserves with teams of young volunteers). During the period of 1964-1967 he served as the director of the Kindrogan Field Centre in Scotland (where he ran the first Scottish field centre and taught ecology courses to school and university students and arranged specialist courses for naturalists, including an annual fungus workshop). His next position, during the period of 1967-1971, was that of a Conservation Officer for Hertfordshire and Middlesex, as an Advisory Teacher in Rural Studies, and also serving as Director of the Chorleywood Field Centre. This was first county conservation officer post in the United Kingdom, and he was in charge of the acquisition and management of nature reserves in two counties, including the use of young volunteers, advising schools in Hertfordshire on using their campus for teaching ecology and biodiversity, training teachers in field biology, and running introductory field work classes for local primary school children from the Watford area, much of which is London overspill. All three posts were held simultaneously.

Bruce then moved on in 1971 to become a Lecturer in Biology at Chester College of Education, which became over a period of time the Chester College of Higher Education, then University College, and finally the University of Chester. He taught full-time until 1994 and then part-time until 2013. He was a Professor of Environmental Biology from 1999 onwards and then was recognized as an Emeritus Professor of Applied Science in 2013.

Bruce and his wife Ellie, have lived in London, Scotland, Hertfordshire and Mold, in North Wales, but since 2010 they have lived in the northern Scottish Highlands overlooking the sea, islands and mountains.

Bruce found his first specimen of a myxomycete in his first week at university in 1957 and decided that this was his field! From the start he was in regular communication with G.W. Martin and C.J. Alexopoulos and later worked with N.E. Nannenga-Bremekamp. He joined the British Mycological Society (B.M.S.) in 1960 and became a regular attendee at field meetings and forays, including overseas meetings (Fig. 1). In all stages of his career, he has made use of every opportunity to collect and study myxomycetes, and also to encourage students to at least look at them! He has attended more B.M.S. forays than most and organised a great many! In the B.M.S. he served as Council member, Centenary Committee member, Foray Secretary (organizing field meetings and some conferences), Conservation Adviser (two stints), and Vice President. As the United Kingdom representative, Bruce was a member of the European Council for the Conservation of Fungi from 1988 to 1995 and was President from 1992 to 1995. Naturally, 'fungi' included myxomycetes!

Figure 1. Bruce Ing (left) and a local naturalist (right) doing field work in the United Kingdom.

In 1993 Bruce organized the first International Congress on the systematics and ecology of myxomycetes (ICSEM), which was held in Chester. The importance of this meeting is attested to by the eleven meetings of the congress held all over the world since the initial meeting. It really opened up communication among specialists in the field of myxobiology. To those who know him, Bruce has always been an enthusiastic and knowledgeable professor, often including historic details and references from the

classics in his lectures. He has organised and lead numerous forays and collected fungi as well as myxomycetes.

Bruce has collected or worked on fresh material of myxomycetes from six continents, including Antarctica and Macronesia, and more than 50 countries. His herbarium will, in due course, be deposited at the Royal Botanic Gardens, Edinburgh, Scotland. Some of the more important publications by Bruce and fellow workers and students are listed below.

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